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A pilot assimilation of glider data in TOPAZ3

by

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Abstract

This report investigates the possibility of and benefits from the assimilation of in-situ S and T observations from gliders in TOPAZ3 system.

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1. Introduction

TOPAZ3 (Bertino and Lisæter 2008) is an operational sea-ice data assimilation system for North Atlantic and Arctic regions based on the HYCOM model and ensemble Kalman filter (EnKF) (e.g. Evensen 2009). The model grid has 880×800 horizontal cells and 22 vertical layers. The horizontal resolution varies between $1/6$ and $1/8$ of a degree. The model state vector contains about $8 \cdot 10^7$ elements.

TOPAZ3 uses an ensemble of 100 model states that is integrated and updated in a weekly data assimilation cycle. Currently the the following observations are assimilated: altimetry SLA, altimetry SST, in-situ salinity (S) and temperature (T) from ARGO profiles, sea ice concentration, and sea ice drift.

The purpose of this report is the investigation of possibility and benefits from the assimilation of in-situ S and T data from gliders. The workflow was supposed to use the existing one for assimilating data from ARGO profiles, with the necessary modification to be made to account for variations in horizontal position.

2. Data and methods

2a. Data

The assimilated data was collected by in the period from 25 August 2009 to 29 August 2009 at the location between 19.92E , 72.34N and 20.37E , 72.65N . It contains total of 40977 records. Each record contains time, latitude, longitude, depth, S , and T fields.

Figures 1 and 2 show the original T and S observations.

Figure 1: Salinity observations (every 40th record).

Figure 2: Temperature observations (every 40th record).

Figure 3: Salinity superobservations.

2b. Preprocessing: first superobing

To simplify quality control and to avoid unnecessary computational load, the standard data preprocessing in TOPAZ3 involves merging the observations into “superobservations” that are specified based on the horizontal model grid and observation time. In the normal TOPAZ3 workflow the “superobing” is only performed for SLA and SST data. The details may change for the next version of the system or after changing the particular data products used, but in the whole there was/is only a need superobing for 2D (surface) observations.

For superobing of in-situ glider data, the data was binned according to its horizontal grid indices, a vertical layer number calculated on the assumption of 10 m thick layers, and the day of the observation. The parameters of each superobservations are calculated as an average of the primary observations merged, except for the variance, which is calculated as inverse of the sum of the inverse variances of primary observations. Note that the vertical layers used in the first superobing was rather crude and could be refined in an operational setup. Unlike for some other models, it is not possible to use the model’s vertical grid at this stage because of its dynamic character in HYCOM. The “vertical” superobing can be only conducted at a later stage, after reading the layer information for at least one ensemble member.

Figures 3 and 4 show the superobservations of T and S after the first superobing. In total, the 40977 original records were merged into 277 superobservations of T and S .

Figure 4: Temperature superobservations.

2c. Second superobing and quality control

The second superobing has been conducted prior to the EnKF analysis, before calculating the forecast ensemble observations. In this process, for each horizontal grid cell, maximum one superobservations has been left in each layer of the first ensemble member. After that, for each superobservation, forecast observations are calculated for each ensemble member. An ensemble of forecast superobservations (“ensemble observations”) makes it possible to calculate the ensemble observations variance. This value is then compared to the observation error variance and to the innovation. If the innovation is greater than the doubled sum of the standard deviation of the ensemble observation and standard deviation of the observation error, then the observation is considered to be either an outlier or have a potential to overstress the model after the update, and discarded. This was the only quality control (QC) performed for the assimilated data set, and it seems to be sufficient in this case.

The observation error variance depends mainly on the used values of the observation error variance of the primary observations, which were assumed to be $(2C)^2$ for T and $(0.1\text{PSU})^2$ for S . The number of observations reduced to 87 after the send superobing, and further to 85 for S and 82 for T after the QC. Oke et al. (2009) used much lower variances, of $(0.5C)^2$ and $(0.05\text{PSU})^2$, but in our case these values result in a big number of rejected observations.

Figures 5 and 5 show the innovations of S and T for the superobservations. The

Figure 5: Salinity innovation.

vertical structure of observations in these figures reflects the vertical structure of the model in the observation region. For S the model is fresher than observations at surface and saltier below pycnocline. For T the model is warmer at surface, and considerably warmer between 50 and 200m.

In total, the observations were combined into 9 “profiles”. Figures 7–15 compare the observations and the model for each of these profiles. In these figures red colour refers to observations, black – to the model. A cross denotes a discarded (not assimilated) observation. Horizontal bars correspond to the standard deviations; those drawn by dashed lines – observations with modified standard deviations for an easier assimilation into the model. The dots in the right lower panel correspond to the locations of the upper observation in each profile; the thick dot corresponds to the location of the profile in hand. These figures confirm the conclusions based on innovations. Interestingly, the match of the model density and the observed density (calculated from T and S) is generally much better than either that for S or T .

2d. Analysis

The EnKF analysis has been conducted using 50 members of a forecast ensemble from 26 August 2009 and the current development version of the EnKF code from NERSC. The localisation support radius has been set equal to 300km, with the taper function by Gaspari and Cohn (1999). The analysis was calculated using the DEnKF scheme by Sakov and Oke (2008).

Figure 6: Temperature innovation.

Figure 7: Profile 1.

Figure 8: Profile 2.

Figure 9: Profile 3.

Figure 10: Profile 4.

Figure 11: Profile 5.

Figure 12: Profile 6.

Figure 13: Profile 7.

Figure 14: Profile 8.

Figure 15: Profile 9.

Figure 16: S , layer 1.

Figure 17: S , layer 4.

3. Results

Figures 16–23 compare forecast and analysis of S and T for model layers 1, 4, 7 and 13. Note that the interface between layer 1 and layer 2 has depth of $z_1 = 3\text{m}$; $z_4 = 14.4\text{m}$; $z_7 = 30.7\text{m}$; and $86.6 < z_{13} < 270\text{m}$. The increment of S is rather moderate, reaching about 0.05PSU for layer 4, while the increment of T is about 0.5C at layers 4 and 7.

The positive corrections of T for layer 13 to the north and north-east of the last profile are probably caused by correlation of T anomaly at these location in the model with anomalies of S or T at the locations of observations.

Figure 18: S , layer 7.

Figure 19: S , layer 13.

Figure 20: T , layer 1.

Figure 21: T , layer 4.

Figure 22: T , layer 7.

Figure 23: T , layer 13.

4. Discussion and conclusions

In this study we conducted a pilot assimilation of the subsurface observations of S and T into TOPAZ3 data assimilation system. The system showed a rather robust performance with a noticeable correction of the S and T fields, strongest at the pycnocline depth.

Overall, the assimilated data was not expected to result in a major impact on a regional system such as TOPAZ3, due to the limited region of observations; however, the in-situ glider observations can be used for producing a targeted hindcast of the ocean state at the time and location of interest. They can also be expected to have a larger impact in smaller scale system.

Apart from being used for data assimilation, the subsurface observations by gliders represent a valuable oceanographic resource, particularly for the North Atlantic and Arctic region, due to the scarcity of subsurface observations in those regions. From data assimilation perspective, they may be used for verification purposes as well as for studying of the subgrid variability.

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